

Peer Tutoring, Teacher-Student-Consultation and Sitting Arrangement as Correlates of Hard-of-Hearing Students' Academic Attainment In Owerri Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated Peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement as correlates of hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State. Correlational design of quantitative nature was adopted for this study. Also, convenience sampling method was used to select 300 hard-of-hearing students as participants for the study from fifteen randomly selected secondary schools in Owerri Imo State. Three research questions were answered and three hypotheses tested. Data collected using four standardized instruments were analyzed using Multiple Regression and Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that that significant positive relationship exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment. The highest significant relative impact on hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment is that of teacher-student consultation. Peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) made 68.5% joint impact on the academic attainment of hard-of-hearing students. Also peer tutoring, teacher-student consultation, and sitting arrangement has positive and significant correlation with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment. Therefore, it was recommended that during teaching and learning engagement, hard-of-hearing students should be given the needed support that will help them develop capacity to actively utilize peer tutoring method to positively enhance their academic performance.

Keywords: Academic attainment, Hard-of-hearing, teacher-student consultation, Peer tutoring, seating arrangement, School and Students

Introduction

The principal focus of secondary education globally is focused on helping learners develop the capacity they need to develop critical thinking mindset, have the ability to apply creative and rational problem solving skills in a distinctive manner. This is necessary because it will help to set the basic foundation required for significant lifelong learning dispositions and career development. This is quite important considering the fact that the learning projection for students' is such that gives them the ample privilege to harness their potentials, realize their innate talent and express the passion that will ignite the prospect of fruitful career development (Mazor, 2024). This suggests the fact that secondary education is a vital spring board needed to guaranty productive character formation, build sound intellectual, moral, emotional and social capabilities in a holistic manner. For instance, learning exposure in secondary school enable students to analysis issues appropriately, engage meaningfully in public discuss, and project issues vibrantly while considering other people's opinions (Mart, 2024). However, accomplishing the above-mentioned might be quite frustrating for students' with hard-of-hearing challenges learning within inclusive. This could be due to their inability to effectively comprehend teachers' expressions while teaching (Mart, 2024).

Students having challenges of hard-of-hearing within inclusive school learning environment often express frustration towards learning if they lack the necessary support to make their learning experience fruitful and result oriented (Mart, 2024). The affirmation of World Health Organisation in their 2024 report indicate that about 430 million people who constitute approximately 5% of global population are observed to be experiencing some measure of hearing loss that needs rehabilitation to enhance functionality. And among this sets of individuals are over 34 million children. This report further indicates that at the year 2050, over 700 million people would be experiencing the challenge of hearing loss. Hard-of-hearing is a phenomenon that indicates the manifestation of hearing loss that could require the use of hearing aid to enhance hearing ability of an individual while processing speech (World Health Organisation, 2024). The academic achievement of students' implies their attained learning outcome during exposure to teaching and learning experience in an academic institutional environment (Doggrell, 2023). This is a vital indicator use in measuring the quality of learning experience a learner is opportune to acquire (Doggrell, 2023). The measure of learners' academic achievement is an important indicator of students' academic performance and it serves as a critical means use to evaluate the quality of learning and the eventual outcome (Silva & Almeida, 2023). Students experiencing hard-of-hearing can perform poorly in an inclusive school learning environment. This could manifest as appropriate learning attention might not be given to students with hard-of-hearing student. This could make them feel excluded and isolated from benefiting from classroom teaching and learning experience.

However, it is of note that the use of peer tutoring technique is an effective mechanism that helps poor performing students to overcome their learning inadequacies and develop the capacity to significantly improve in their academic performance positively (Ojha & Mishra, 2014). The research findings of Ullah, et al, (2018) acknowledges that peer tutoring is a creatively strategic procedure that allows more knowledgeable and intellectually competent students' to pragmatically help teach poor performing students in a dynamic way and make learning meaningful to them. This measure help poor performing students' develop the capacity to positively improve in their study habit and in their academic attainment. For example, research report affirmed that peer tutoring serves as an important strategic method use to positively support the learning needs of poor achieving learners with hard-of-hearing challenges (Ullah, et al, 2018). The use of peer tutoring teaching mechanism has vibrant impact in motivating students with hard of hearing problem to positively improve their learning and problem solving skills in a significant manner through purposeful intellectual socialization, encouragement and support via positive tutees-tutors learning relationship and discuss (Ullah, et al, 2018). Literature document peer tutoring meaning of teaching as a good strategic option that help foster positive academic and socio-emotional adjustment and enable the attainment of high academic performance among hearing impaired learners (Ubah, et al, 2022).

The research effort of Baleni et al (2016) which focused on determining if peer tutoring significantly predicts the academic attainment of hearing impaired learners through the use of quantitative research method found that hearing impaired students who attended peer tutoring classes had high scores in their examination than those that did not attend who equally had learning challenges beforehand. Baleni et al (2016) stated that the use of peer tutoring meanings of teaching is quite cost effective in providing adequate socio-emotional and learning support that can help poor performing learners in school to develop the learning capacity that will help them adjust positively and overcome barriers associated to learning. Equally, Kim et al (2021) posits that peer tutoring often help to significantly reduce the rate of failure experienced by hearing impaired learners.

Researchers affirmed that students with hard-of-hearing that consult with their teachers on academic issues record high academic performance. This sets of students are often active in class learning activities, attain positive feedback and evaluations from teachers that further help motivate them to develop positive attitude towards learning (Chen et al., 2021; Pham et al., 2022). Positive evaluations and feedback which learners attain from teachers via teacher and students consultation is found to foster the development of high self-concept and academic improvement (Chen et al., 2021), and it consequently ignites readiness and positive interest towards learning and school activities (Pham et al., 2022). Likewise, the positive academic

and intellectual gain attain when students consult with teachers is well documented by several studies (Li, 2022; Qonita et al., 2021; Zee & Roorda, 2018) and they specifically emphasize that consulting with teachers help foster in students' the passion and determination to learning and focus on excelling in their academic engagement.

Furthermore, the report of studies Van Herpen et al (2020); Qonita et al (2021) categorically indicates that learners who consult with their teachers often receive firm psycho-inspirational academic support that inspire them to adopt positive attitude towards learning and devote quality time to studying for better result. Coristine et al (2022) stated that Teacher and student consultation is pivotal to igniting positive and well enriched teaching and classroom learning experience. This experience spurs students to develop needed self-confidence that would stimulate them to engage in appropriate academic learning risk taking behaviour (Coristine et al, 2022). Without ambiguity, teacher and student consultation is a pragmatic learning phenomenon vital to use in creating a rewarding teaching and learning environment because it makes learners have an enterprising sense of belongingness and feel committed to attaining success in their academic endeavours (Buffet, 2019).

Authorities González et al (2021); Gao et al (2022) established that the pattern of sitting arrangement adopted in a classroom setting has significant implication on attention learners pay in class during teaching, how visible they see the chalkboard and engagement in classroom learning activities. The finding of Bekkering (2020) research study indicates that classroom sitting arrangement has high positive correlation with learners' active participation in learning activities and their level of academic achievement. Allowing hearing impaired students to sit at vintage position in front of the class has been shown to have positive impact on their academic achievement (Byiringiro, 2023; Weinstein, 2019).

Blume et al (2019) established that front sit learners comprehend learning activities better and equally record better academic performance in most situations than students that sit at the back. The appropriate use of good sitting pattern in a classroom has been documented to positive motivating impact on learners learning dispositions and their performance in academic task. For example, Evans et al (2019) and Norazman et al (2019) report reveal that a well-coordinated sitting arrangement in a class has the potential of fostering the attainment of positive attentive responses from learners and equally promoting quality learning. Considering the above context, this study is hinged on the postulations of Ryan and Deci (2017) Self-determination theory (SDT) theoretical affirmations. These affirmations highlights that human behaviour is positively projected on a determined frame of mind and self-consciousness if competence, relatedness and autonomy to dispose of once potentials and innate capabilities are guaranteed. When

there are possibilities to attain these dispositions, concerned learner in a learning environment will be specifically determined and motivated to be resilient and committed to achieve success in their academic pursuit even in the face of rigorous negative challenges. This makes this theory relevant and applicable for use in this study.

Statement of the Problem

Hard-of-hearing learners often express frustration when they are not given the support they need to excel in their academic pursuit. They can feel neglected by teachers when they find it difficult to consult with them on issues concerning their academic and general wellbeing. When this experience occurs, students with hard-of-hearing can express sense of helplessness, become devastated and maladjusted. This development can have long lasting negative effect on their daily functioning, sense of reasoning and active participation in classroom learning activities. This makes it imperative to investigate peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement as correlates of hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to through empirical procedure investigate peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement as correlates of hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State and to specifically:

1. Find out the kind of relationship that exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State
2. Know the relative impact made by each of the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri, Imo State)
3. Find out the joint impact made by the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri, Imo State).

Research Question

1. What kind of relationship that exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State?

2. What relative impact did each of the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) have on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State)?
3. What joint impact do the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) have on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State)?

Research Hypotheses

1. Peer tutoring will correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri, Imo State.
2. Teacher-student-consultation will correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri, Imo State.
3. Sitting arrangement will correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri, Imo State.

Methods

Correlational design of quantitative nature was adopted for this study. Also, convenience sampling method was used to select 300 hard-of-hearing students as participants for the study from fifteen randomly selected secondary schools in Owerri Imo State.

Instruments

Hard-of-hearing Students Cognitive Cumulative Records for first and second term examinations were used to measure their academic attainment. These records were obtained with the support of the school Principals and Class Teachers.

Peer Tutoring Core Competency Test for College Students (Kim et al., 2019) is a standardized instrument and it was used to measure the beneficial outcome of peer tutoring class activities. It is a 5-point Likert response format scale ranging from (1 = not at all true, to 5 = very true). It has internal reliability of $\alpha = .83$

Student-Teacher Relationship Scale (Wang, 2016) is a scale that has being used across cultures to measure pattern of teacher-student consultation. It has 22 items and a 5-point Likert response pattern from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree). A high score implies positive teacher-student consultations. It has internal reliability of $\alpha = .91$

Students’ Classroom Sitting Arrangement Questionnaire was used in measuring the implication of classroom sitting pattern on students’ academic attainment. It is a 7 item researcher’s made instrument with 4-point Likert rating response pattern. It has internal reliability coefficient of 0.81.

Method of Data Administration

Visitations were made to the schools used for the study by the researchers and got permission from the school management to conduct the study. The researchers also got the consent of the participants, explained the reason for conducting the research and them administered the questionnaires to them with necessary explanations on how to complete them. Thereafter, the questionnaires were collected back for data analyses.

Method of Data Analyses

Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression to answer the research question and test the hypotheses of the study at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: 1. What kind of relationship that exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment in Owerri Imo State?

Table 1: Showing the kind of relationship that exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment in Owerri Imo State

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	1	2	3	4
Hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment	300	72.51	13.68	1.000			
Peer tutoring	300	56.23	9.13	.523	1.000		
Teacher-student-consultation	300	61.48	11.06	.659	.524	1.000	
Sitting arrangement	300	53.38	8.72	.436	.411	.395	1.000

The result presented in the Table 1 above shows the kind of relationship that exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment in

Owerri, Imo State. The results reveals that significant positive relationship exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri, Imo State. It shows that the independent variables have positive correlational effect on hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment.

Research Question Two: 2. What relative impact did each of the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) have on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State)?

Table 2: Highlighting the relative impact each of the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) have on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment

Variables	B	Std.Error	Beta	T	Sig
Peer tutoring	.412	.045	.231	3.270	.000
Teacher-student-consultation	.447	.053	.496	5.416	.000
Sitting arrangement	.357	.041	.192	2.794	.000

The result highlights of table 2 indicates that each of the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) have diverse measures of significant relative impact on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment). As observed, from the information on the table, the highest significant relative impact on hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment is that of teacher-student consultation.

Research Question 3: What joint impact do the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) have on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State)

Table 3: Showing the joint impact of the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) on the dependent variable (hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment in Owerri Imo State)

R= .774					
R ² = .685					
Adj R ² = .540					
Std Error= 7.113					
Source	Df	Sum squares (ss)	Mean square	F-Ratio	Sig
Regression	3	14042.081	4680.694	58.79	.000
Residual	296	23568.002	79.62		
Total	299	37610.083			

The result on table 3 above revealed that the independent variables (peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement) made 68.5% joint impact on the academic attainment of hard-of-hearing students. The multiple regression result further produced an F-ratio (3/296) = 58.79 that is significant at: $p < 0.05$ alpha level.

Ho1: Peer tutoring will correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment in Owerri Imo State.

Table 4: Showing peer tutoring correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	P
Hard-of-hearing secondary school students’ academic attainment	300	72.51	13.68	.523	298	Sig
Peer tutoring	300	56.23	9.13			

The highlighted results in table 4 indicates that peer tutoring has positive and significantly correlate with hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment; $r (298) = .523, p < .05$. In view of this development, the result of the hypotheses is accepted.

Ho2: Teacher-student-consultation will correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students’ academic attainment in Owerri Imo State.

Table 5: Showing teacher-student consultation correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	P
Hard-of-hearing secondary school students' academic attainment	300	72.51	13.68	.659	298	Sig
Teacher-student consultation	300	61.48	11.06			

The highlighted results in table 5 indicates that teacher-student-consultation has positive and significant correlation with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment; $r(298) = .659, p < .05$. In view of this development, the result of the hypotheses is accepted.

Ho3: Sitting arrangement will correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State.

Table 6: Showing sitting arrangement correlate significantly with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	Df	P
hard-of-hearing secondary school students' academic attainment	300	72.51	13.68	.436	298	Sig
Sitting arrangement	300	53.38	8.72			

The highlighted results in table 6 indicates that sitting arrangement has positive and significant correlation with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment; $r(298) = .436, p < .05$. In view of this development, the result of the hypotheses is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The outcome of the first research question shows that significant positive relationship exist between peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation, sitting arrangement and hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment in Owerri Imo State. The reason could be that sincere consultation with teachers often motivate and inspire students' to strive for greater height of success. This concurs with the finding of previous studies. For example, Chen et al (2021) and Pham et al (2022) affirmed that students with hard-of-hearing that consult with their teachers on academic issues record high academic performance. This sets of students are often active in class learning activities, attain positive feedback and evaluations from teachers that further help motivate them to develop positive attitude towards learning.

The finding of the second research question revealed that the highest significant relative impact on hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment is made by teacher-student consultation. This development aligns to the fact that Positive evaluations and feedback which learners attain from teachers via teacher and students consultation is found to foster the development of high self-concept and academic improvement (Chen et al., 2021), and it consequently ignites readiness and positive interest towards learning and school activities (Pham et al., 2022). Likewise, the positive academic and intellectual gain attain when students consult with teachers is well documented by several studies (Li, 2022; Qonita et al., 2021; Zee & Roorda, 2018) and they specifically emphasize that consulting with teachers help foster in students' the passion and determination to learning and focus on excelling in their academic engagement.

Likewise, the outcome of the third research question shows that peer tutoring, teacher-student-consultation and sitting arrangement made a significant 68.5% joint impact on the academic attainment of hard-of-hearing students. This result affirms that the principal focus of secondary education globally is focused on helping learners develop the capacity they need to develop critical thinking mindset, have the ability to apply creative and rational problem solving skills in a distinctive manner. This is necessary because it will help to set the basic foundation required for significant lifelong learning dispositions and career development. This is quite important considering the fact that the learning projection for students' is such that gives them the ample privilege to harness their potentials, realize their innate talent and express the passion that will ignite the prospect of fruitful career development (Mazor, 2024).

The finding of the first hypotheses indicates that peer tutoring has positive and significantly correlate with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment. This shows that the use of peer tutoring is a vibrant means of support the academic and intellectual development of poor performing hard-of-hearing students. This corroborates the report of Ojha and Mishra (2014) which affirmed that the use of peer tutoring technique is an effective mechanism that helps poor performing students to overcome their learning inadequacies and develop the capacity to significantly improve in their academic performance positively. The research findings of Ullah, et al, (2018) acknowledges that peer tutoring is a creatively strategic procedure that allows more knowledgeable and intellectually competent students' to pragmatically help teach poor performing students in a dynamic way and make learning meaningful to them. This measure help poor performing students' develop the capacity to positively improve in their study habit and in their academic attainment.

The outcome of the second hypotheses indicates that teacher-student-consultation has positive and significant correlation with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment. This is in line with report of

previous research findings. As observed, the report of studies Van Herpen et al (2020); Qonita et al (2021) categorically indicates that learners who consult with their teachers often receive firm psycho-inspirational academic support that inspire them to adopt positive attitude towards learning and devote quality time to studying for better result. Coristine et al (2022) stated that Teacher and student consultation is pivotal to igniting positive and well enriched teaching and classroom learning experience. This experience spurs students to develop needed self-confidence that would stimulate them to engage in appropriate academic learning risk taking behaviour (Coristine et al, 2022).

The finding of the third hypotheses indicates that sitting arrangement has positive and significant correlation with hard-of-hearing students' academic attainment. This result corroborate those of González et al (2021); Gao et al (2022) who established that the pattern of sitting arrangement adopted in a classroom setting has significant implication on attention learners pay in class during teaching, how visible they see the chalkboard and engagement in classroom learning activities. Also, the finding of Bekkering (2020) research study indicates that classroom sitting arrangement has high positive correlation with learners' active participation in learning activities and their level of academic achievement. Allowing hearing impaired students to sit at vintage position in front of the class has been shown to have positive impact on their academic achievement (Byiringiro, 2023; Weinstein, 2019).

Recommendations

1. During teaching and learning engagement, hard-of-hearing students should be given the needed support that will help them develop capacity to actively utilize peer tutoring method to positively enhance their academic performance.
2. Teacher-student consultation is a vital means of motivating learners and supporting their academic drive. Therefore, hard-of-hearing students should be given appropriate orientation concerning the benefits.
3. Classroom sitting arrangement should be organized in a way and manner that addresses the needs of learners.

Conclusion

The need to help hard-of-hearing students in inclusive learning environment not to feel isolated and frustrated require teachers to encourage them to engage in peer tutoring classes, teacher-student consultation and be well sited in classroom as a means to address and meet their educational and developmental needs and make learning meaningful to them.

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